

Synthesis, Characterisation and Antimicrobial Activities of Metal Chelates derived from α -Oximinoacetoacet-*o/p*-toluidide Thiosemicarbazone

P. S. PATEL^a, R. M. RAY^b and M. M. PATEL^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Biosciences, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

Manuscript received 11 March 1992, revised 16 November 1992, accepted 2 December 1992

Metal complexes of α -oximinoacetoacet-*o/p*-toluidide thiosemicarbazones (OAOTTS and OAPTTS) with Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and UO₂^{II} have been prepared and characterised by elemental analyses, conductivity, differential scanning calorimetry study, thermogravimetric analyses and infrared and electronic spectral measurements in conjunction with magnetic susceptibility measurements. They have also been tested for their antibacterial activities.

The coordination chemistry of thiosemicarbazones assumed new importance because of the recent observations about the antibacterial and antitumour activities of some thiosemicarbazones and a few of their metal complexes¹. Antimicrobial activity of thiosemicarbazone has been attributed to its metal chelating capacity which titrate out essential elements required for growth of micro-organisms². Thiosemicarbazone which comprises a well known group of nitrogen and sulphur donors, has been extensively used for complex formation³.

The present communication reports α -oximinoacetoacet-*o*-toluidide thiosemicarbazone (OAOTTS), α -oximinoacetoacet-*p*-toluidide thiosemicarbazone (OAPTTS) and its complexes with Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and UO₂^{II}. The OAOTTS and OAPTTS ligands and their metal chelates have been tested for their antimicrobial properties. The structure of the complexes has been established using analytical, physical and spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Magnetic and reflectance spectral studies: The Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature indicating that they have square-planar configuration. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit two bands at 14 915–14 930 and 20 190–20 200 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ¹A_{1g}→¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g}→¹A_{2g} transitions respectively, in favour of the square-planar structure⁴. The Co^{II} complexes show magnetic moment of 4.2–4.3 B.M. which indicates the presence of three unpaired electrons and also suggests the tetrahedral structure for them. The reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 8 775–8 965, 15 310–15 385 and 23 810–25 640 cm⁻¹ which are

assigned to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁ (F), ⁴A₂→⁴T₁ (P) and charge transfer transitions respectively, for tetrahedral geometry⁵. The magnetic moment values of 5.4–5.5 B.M. for the Mn^{II} complex are lower than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) which may be due to partial aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis. The reflectance spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 16 390–16 650, 19 530–19 750 and 23 505–24 641 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to the ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} (⁴G), ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{2g} (⁴G) and ⁶A_{1g}→⁴E_g. ⁴A_{1g} (⁴G) transitions respectively, considering an octahedral symmetry. The reflectance spectra of the dioxouranium(VI) chelates exhibit two bands at 20 835–21 740 and 24 690–25 315 cm⁻¹, assigned to the ¹Σ_g⁺→³π_u and charge transfer transitions respectively, for octahedral stereochemistry⁶. The Zn^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic⁷.

Infrared spectral study: Complete assignment of all the absorptions of the ligands is not attempted here, only a prominent few, essential for the determination of the bonding sites in the ligands are assigned. The absence of absorption due to ν_{SH} at about 2 580 cm⁻¹ indicates that the ligand remains in thioketo form (I) at least in the solid state⁸. However, in solution, the existence of thioketo (I) and thioenol (II) tautomerism may be likely.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CHELATES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	σ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Activation energy eV
		M	N	S			
OAOTTS	White	—	23.79 (23.89)	10.81 (10.92)	—	2.95×10^{-12}	0.158
Ni-OAOTTS	Chocolate	16.65 (16.78)	19.91 (20.01)	9.04 (9.15)	dimag.	2.96×10^{-12}	0.150
Co-OAOTTS	Brown	16.73 (16.84)	19.90 (20.00)	9.01 (9.14)	4.15	2.9×10^{-12}	0.0976
Mn-(OAOTTS).2H ₂ O	Brown	18.21 (18.32)	18.23 (18.32)	8.30 (8.36)	5.44	2.15×10^{-11}	0.0465
Zn-OAOTTS	Yellow	18.11 (18.24)	19.44 (19.53)	8.80 (8.92)	dimag.	2.36×10^{-12}	0.1098
Hg-OAOTTS	Light yellow	40.71 (40.80)	14.15 (14.23)	6.42 (6.50)	dimag.	3.15×10^{-12}	0.0744
Cd-OAOTTS	Dull yellow	27.77 (27.86)	17.23 (17.35)	7.85 (7.93)	dimag.	2.05×10^{-11}	0.03
UO ₂ -(OAOTTS).2H ₂ O	Brick red	45.10 (45.22)	11.61 (11.72)	5.26 (5.35)	dimag.	3.65×10^{-12}	0.0835
OAPTTS	White	—	23.77 (23.89)	10.80 (10.92)	—	7.68×10^{-13}	0.141
Ni-OAPTTS	Chocolate	16.66 (16.78)	19.92 (20.01)	9.01 (9.14)	dimag.	3.15×10^{-13}	0.0496
Co-OAPTTS	Dark brown	16.71 (16.84)	19.90 (20.00)	9.03 (9.14)	4.24	7.28×10^{-14}	0.039
Mn-(OAPTTS).2H ₂ O	Brown	18.20 (18.32)	18.24 (18.32)	8.29 (8.37)	5.5	8.41×10^{-13}	0.07
Zn-OAPTTS	Yellow	18.11 (18.24)	19.43 (19.53)	8.81 (8.92)	dimag.	4.98×10^{-14}	0.0298
Cd-OAPTTS	Yellow	40.72 (40.80)	14.13 (14.23)	6.42 (6.50)	dimag.	1.89×10^{-13}	0.0437
Hg-OAPTTS	Dull yellow	27.75 (27.86)	17.22 (17.35)	7.84 (7.93)	dimag.	9.13×10^{-12}	0.0155
UO ₂ -(OAPTTS).2H ₂ O	Brick red	45.10 (45.22)	11.62 (11.72)	5.23 (5.35)	dimag.	5.27×10^{-12}	0.0189

The C=O stretching frequency appears at about 1660 cm^{-1} as a very strong absorption⁹. It shows a blue-shift of about 10 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates. This blue-shift may be traced to the breaking of hydrogen bond between C=O and N—OH moiety. This replacement of hydrogen bond is further supported by the disappearance of ligand peak at $2700\text{--}2800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ after complex formation. The characteristic absorption due to N—O stretching of N—OH moiety in the ligand occurs¹⁰ at about 950 cm^{-1} . This disappears in the complexes and a new band around 1320 cm^{-1} assigned to N—O stretching appears¹¹. This suggests the presence of M—N—O bonding. In comparison with the comparable molecules the frequency at about 850 cm^{-1} in the ligands may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ ¹². On complexation, this band completely disappears, and a new band around 660 cm^{-1} appears which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$. This indicates the presence of M—S—C bonding in the metal complexes. The use of the absorption due to C=N stretching frequency in identifying the bonding site is somewhat limited here because of the complex nature of absorption in the region $1550\text{--}1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, the strong peak of the ligands at about 1610 cm^{-1} registers substantial decrease in the intensity after complex formation. This band may be assigned to complex vibration involving $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, δ_{NH_2} and the benzene ring^{9,13}. The band due to the ligands at about 1545 cm^{-1} probably a coupled vibration

of δ^{NH} (of HNCO moiety) and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, shifts to about 1520 cm^{-1} after complexation¹³. The $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ band in the ligands is observed at about 1055 cm^{-1} . This band shifts to about 1040 cm^{-1} in the complexes¹⁴. Thus it is concluded that the ligand would have behaved as a dibasic tridentate for the parent complexes. The band at $3350\text{--}3370 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Mn^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes shows the presence of coordinated water molecule¹⁵. Since the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 1, at least dimerisation is required to achieve four- and six-coordination in the complexes reported. Insolubility of the complexes in common organic solvents itself also to some extent, supports the proposed dimeric structure¹⁶.

Electrical conductivity study: The electrical conductivity of the ligands and its metal chelates was studied over a wide range of temperature. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ is the conductivity at T (K), σ_0 the specific conductivity, E_a the activation energy and k the Boltzman constant. The activation energy decreases in the order: OAOTTS > Ni > Zn > Co > UO₂ > Hg > Mn > Cd, and OAPTTS > Mn > Ni > Hg > Co > Zn > UO₂ > Cd, which is in partial agreement with reported results¹⁷.

Thermal study: The examination of the results of TG and DSC (Table 2) reveals that the metal

TABLE 2—THERMAL DATA OF THE LIGAND AND CHELATES

Compd.	TG			E_a kcal/ mol	Order or reaction (<i>n</i>)	DSC			
	T_S °C	T_E °C	Weight- loss %			T_S °C	T_E °C	Peak temp. °C	ΔH J/g
OAOTTS	210	330	75.0	6.29	1	205	270	254	25.83
Ni-OAOTTS	295	365	50.0	3.93	1	30	350	341	31.25
Co-OAOTTS	245	290	45.0	3.46	1	255	295	285	47.11
Zn-OAOTTS	310	370	43.0	5.58	1	300	370	360	55.76
Mn(OAOTTS).2H ₂ O	230	300	52.0	4.18	1	375	395	390	20.22
Cd-OAOTTS	240	350	44.0	3.57	1	235	305	293	24.05
Hg-OAOTTS	260	320	55.0	3.73	1	290	340	329	57.2
UO ₂ (OAOTTS).2H ₂ O	315	420	60.0	4.58	1	250	315	303	41.41
OAPTTS	195	320	72.0	6.18	1	310	360	358	28.70
Ni-OAPTTS	310	355	48.0	4.65	?	205	295	283	30.13
Co-OAPTTS	255	300	50.0	3.00	1	300	350	335	35.28
Zn-OAPTTS	305	370	43.0	5.28	1	260	295	285	44.05
Mn-(OAPTTS).2H ₂ O	210	290	49.0	4.38	1	310	365	354	50.55
Cd-OAPTTS	255	340	52.3	3.82	1	370	390	385	17.81
Hg-OAPTTS	250	315	57.0	3.65	1	220	275	262	30.15
UO ₂ -(OAPTTS).2H ₂ O	305	405	62.0	4.03	1	245	330	301	43.33
						265	300	287	45.88
						309	370	366	34.49

T_S = Starting temperature ; T_E = ending temperature.

chelates follow a single-step decomposition. From TG traces it is observed that the rate of decomposition of the metal chelates is faster than that of the parent ligand. The Broido method was applied to TG data to determine the energy of activation and the order of the reaction¹⁸. The two water molecules in the Mn^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes were lost around 170°, indicating that these molecules are coordinated to the respective metal ion¹⁹. The trend in thermal stability of the metal chelates on the basis of E_a values in decreasing order is as follows: OAOTTS > Zn > UO₂ > Mn > Ni > Hg > Cd > Co, and OAPTTS > Zn > Ni > Mn > UO₂ > Cd > Hg > Co. From DSC traces, it is observed that single step decomposition of ligand and its metal complexes takes place as they show the presence of single exothermic peak. However, in the Zn^{II} chelate a complex exothermic peak is present in all the traces. The reason for this is that the Zn chelate is thermally most stable with high E_a involved in its decomposition process. The metal chelates under study do not undergo any observable physical or chemical changes before their thermal decomposition. The loss of two water molecules is noticed by the presence of endothermic peak in the Mn^{II} and UO₂^{II} traces.

Antimicrobial activities: The ligands and their metal chelates were studied for their antimicrobial behaviour towards *E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*, *B. subtilis*, *S. marcescens*, *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum*. OAOTTS and OAPTTS ligands showed significant inhibition of *P. fluorescens* and *B. subtilis* while *E. coli* and *S. marcescens* were affected to lesser extent. The ligand showed greater inhibition of fungi *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum*. The metal chelates showed remarkable change in biological properties. The Ni and Co chelates showed significant inhibition of *P. fluorescens*. The Cd and Hg chelates showed significant inhibition irrespective of test organisms. The Zn and Mn chelates

also exhibited antimicrobial activities. The metal chelates of OAOTTS ligand except these of Ni and Mn showed inhibition of *A. niger*. *T. longibrachiatum* was inhibited by Cd, Hg, UO₂ and Zn chelates to greater extent than that of Co, Ni and Mn. OAPTTS ligand showed significant inhibition of both the culture (40–80% inhibition).

Thus it is clear that inhibitory power of thio-semicarbazone is not solely due to metal chelation capacity. The metal chelates also showed antimicrobial effect which further showed variation with respect to organisms to organisms as well as metal ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands OAOTTS and OAPTTS were synthesised by the known methods²⁰.

Synthesis of Ni^{II} complexes: To ligand OAOTTS (0.010 mol) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml), was added an aqueous solution (50 ml) of an nickel(II) acetate monohydrate (0.005 mol) was added whereby the chocolate colour product separated out. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 1 h and the resulting solid was washed with hot distilled water, ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The yield was quantitative. The corresponding Co, Mn, Zn, Hg, Cd and UO₂ complexes of OAOTTS and OAPTTS ligands were synthesised by the same method. All the complexes were found insoluble in common organic solvents.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and diffuse reflectance spectra on a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer using magnesium oxide as a reference material. Magnetic studies were made at room temperature by Gouy method using mercurytetrathiocyanatocobalt(II) as a calibrant. Metal estimations were carried out by standard methods²¹. Nitrogen was esti-

mated by Kjeldahl's method and sulphur by fusion method²². The TG and DSC thermograms were scanned on Du-Pont 951 and 900 instruments respectively. The electrical conductivity was measured over a wide range of temperature in air using a Hewlett Packard 4329-A instrument.

Pre-grown cultures of bacteria and fungi were inoculated into N-broth and Sabouraud's dextrose medium respectively. Activities of bacteria on samples were estimated by measuring growth after 48 h using a Systronic digital spectrophotometer at 660 nm. The experiment was carried out with and without sample (500 ppm). Activities of fungi on samples (70 ppm) were determined by measuring the growth after 96 h. The growth was determined as dry cell mass.

References

1. K. N. THIMMAIAH, G. T. CHANDRAPPA, RANZASWAMY and JAYARAMA, *Polyhedron* 1984, 3, 1237; V. S. JOLLY and K. P. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 412; D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, 203.
2. H. STUNZI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1982, 35, 1145.
3. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1975, 15, 279; M. PATEL, M. M. PATEL, A. RAY and M. R. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 509.
4. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry". Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1980; B. SINGH, B. P. YADAV and R. C. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 441.
5. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem Soc.*, 1959, 338.
6. K. P. KARIYA and N. S. BHAVE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 788.
7. S. SHARMA, M. KUMAR and T. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 781.
8. L. J. BELLAMY, "Advances in Infrared Group Frequencies", Methuen, London, 1968.
9. K. NAKANISHI, "IR Absorption Spectroscopy", Nankodo Co. Ltd., Tokyo, 1964.
10. P. A. S. SMITH and J. E. ROBERTSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 84, 1197.
11. A. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. KALIA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 2016.
12. A. RAY and D. N. SATHYANARAYANA, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1975, 31, 899; A. RAY and D. N. SATHYANARAYANA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1974, 47, 729.
13. T. UNO, K. MACHIDA and Y. SATIO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 42, 1539; T. UNO, K. MACHIDA and Y. SATIO, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1970, 26, 2089.
14. K. GEETHARANI and D. N. SATHYANARAYANA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1977, 30, 1617.
15. C. B. MATHO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 51, 935.
16. B. S. SANKHALA, S. MATHUR and MEGHSINGH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1983, 13, 45; M. A. ALI, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and D. J. PHILIPS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 7, 179; J. J. BONNET, A. THOREZ, A. MAISONNAT, J. GALY and R. POILBLANC, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 5941.
17. J. T. D'SA, V. J. RAO, K. C. PATEL and R. D. PATEL, *Angew. Makromol. Chem.*, 1979, 79, 133.
18. A. B. BROIDO, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1969, 7, 1761.
19. M. A. NAKOLAEV, V. A. LOGVINENKO and L. I. MYCHINA, "Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 779.
20. M. R. PATEL, Ph.D. Thesis, S. P. University, Vallabh Vidyanagar, 1963.
21. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1962.
22. A. J. WEINIG and W. P. SCHODER, "Technical Methods of Ore Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1939, p. 233.